
Big Bang as a Critical Attractor in a Discrete Pre-Geometric State Space with Emergent Inflation

Abstract:

Proposed is a pre-geometric cosmological framework in which spacetime and inflation emerge from a discrete graph-based state space. The Big Bang is interpreted not as a temporal singularity but as a critical attractor (or accumulation point) of a high-dimensional dynamical system defined on network configurations. A coarse-graining procedure yields an effective scalar degree of freedom, identified as an emergent inflaton field. Inflation arises as a relaxation process near a degenerate minimum of an effective potential induced by network connectivity and density constraints. The model predicts near scale-invariant perturbations, suppressed tensor modes, and small deviations from Gaussian statistics, potentially distinguishable from standard single-field inflation.

Key-words: Critical attractor; discrete pre-geometry; emergent inflation; graph-description; spacetime-network; fixpoint-structure; relaxation-process; scale-invariance; cosmic perturbations; non-gaussian description.

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1. Introduction:

The standard inflationary paradigm successfully explains the observed homogeneity and isotropy of the Universe as well as the nearly scale-invariant spectrum of primordial perturbations. However, the microscopic origin of the inflaton field and the initial conditions of inflation remain open questions .

In this work, proposed is a pre-geometric description in which spacetime and inflation emerge from a discrete dynamical system defined on a graph-like configuration space. In this framework, the Big Bang corresponds to a critical attractor in the space of configurations rather than a singular event in time. [1.].

2. Pre-Geometric State Space:

Assumed is, that the fundamental degrees of freedom are given by a time-dependent graph:

$$[G=(V, E)] \quad (1.)$$

where (V) denotes nodes and (E) edges encoding adjacency relations.

The system evolves in a configuration space (S_G) equipped with a stochastic or gradient-like dynamics:

$$G=(V, E)$$

$$G_{n+1}=F(G_n) \quad (2.)$$

Assumed is the existence of a coarse density variable $(\rho(G))$, with a critical value (ρ_c) of order:

$$\rho_c \sim l_p^{-4} \quad (3.)$$

where (l_p) denotes the Planck length .

3. Effective Potential and Critical Structure:

Introduced is an effective potential functional:

$$V[G]=\alpha(\rho-\rho_c)^2+\beta\sum_{(i,j)\in E}(k_{ij}-k_c)^2+V_{fluct}[G] \quad (4.)$$

where:

1. (k_{ij}) encodes local connectivity structure,
2. (V_{fluct}) describes microscopic fluctuations.

The system exhibits a highly degenerate minimum manifold:

$$M_0=\{(G \in SG)|_{\rho=\rho_c}; k_{ij} \approx k_c\} \quad (5.)$$

Interpreted is this minimal manifold as a **critical attractor**. Therefor follows now:

4. Big Bang as Critical Attractor:

Defined is the Big Bang as the accumulation of trajectories in configuration space:

$$G_n \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M_0 \quad (6.)$$

or equivalently as a fixed-point-like structure:

$$F(G^{(*)}) \approx G^{(*)} \quad (7.)$$

However, $(G^{(*)})$ is not isolated but lies on a degenerate manifold, implying large fluctuations and enhanced correlations.

Now interpreted is this regime as the effective origin of classical spacetime. Ergo follows:

5. Emergence of Effective Field Theory:

Perform a coarse-graining procedure over graph degrees of freedom:

$$\phi(x) = \langle \psi \rangle_{\text{coarse}} \quad (8.)$$

yielding an emergent scalar field.

The effective low-energy Lagrangian becomes:

$$L_{\text{eff}} = \frac{M_P^2}{2} R + \frac{1}{2} (\partial \phi)^2 + U(\phi) \quad (9a.)$$

with potential of :

$$U(\phi) = U_0 \left(1 - \frac{\phi^2}{\mu^2} \right)^2 \quad (9b.)$$

This assumption corresponds to a symmetric double-well (hilltop-type) inflationary potential. Now there is:

6. Inflation as Relaxation Dynamics:

Inflation arises as slow-roll dynamics near the critical region $\phi \approx 0$:

$$3H\dot{\phi} \approx -U'(\phi) \quad (10.)$$

The slow-roll parameters then are:

$$\epsilon \ll 1; \eta \approx \frac{-M_P^2 \mu^2}{U_0} \quad (11.)$$

leading to:

$$n_s \approx 0.96 - 0.97$$

$$r \sim 10^{-4} - 10^{-3}$$

consistent with observational constraints (Planck-satellite measurements). Therefore now discussed are the:

7. Observational Signatures:

The model predicts deviations from standard single-field inflation:

(i) Non-Gaussianity:

$$f_{NL} \sim O(1) \quad (12.)$$

arising from underlying graph correlations.

(ii) Oscillatory features:

Discrete structure induces modulations of :

$$P(k) = P_0(k) [1 + \alpha \sin(\omega \log k)]; (\alpha \ll 1). \quad (13.)$$

(iii) Tensor suppression:

Due to distributed energy among microscopic degrees of freedom there is:

$$r \ll 10^{-2} \quad (14.)$$

8. Interpretation:

In this framework:

1. Spacetime is emergent,
2. Inflation is a collective relaxation mode,
3. The Big Bang corresponds to a critical attractor in configuration space [2.].

This provides a potential link between discrete quantum gravity approaches and early-universe cosmology [3.].

9. Conclusion:

Proposed is a pre-geometric cosmological model in which:

1. The Big Bang is a critical attractor rather than a singular event,
2. Inflation emerges as an effective scalar field dynamics,
3. Observable signatures may deviate slightly from standard single-field inflation.

Future work should aim at deriving the effective potential $U(\phi)$ from a specified microscopic graph dynamics and confronting the model with high-precision CMB data to conform or reject it.

10. Short discussion:

This model is structural near to emergent gravity [4.], to causal sets [5.],[6.] and to loop-inspired EFTs [7.]. From mathematics it is similar to RG-fixpoints and the physical interpretation is a **microfundation of inflation**. A more detailed paper to this theme will follow.

11. References:

- [1.] --- Döring, H., Emergent Inflation and Cosmological Perturbations from Graph Spectral Geometry. <https://www.academia.edu/165712417> , **2026**.
- [2.] --- Reuter, M., Weyer,H., Background independence and asymptotic safety in conformally reduced gravity, Physical Review D, Particles, Fields, Gravitation, **2009**.
- [3.] --- Connes, A., Non-commutative Geometry and the Spectral Model of Space-time, Quantum Spaces: Poincaré Seminar **2007**, Springer.
- [4.] --- Padmanabhan, T. , Emergent Gravity Paradigm: Recent Progress, arXiv:1410.6285 [gr-qc], **2014**.
- [5.] --- Sorkin, R.D. Indications of causal set cosmology, Int.J.Theor.Phys.39:1731-1736,**2000**, arXiv:gr-qc/0003043 .
- [6.] --- Ambjørn, J., Loll,R., Causal Dynamical Triangulations: New Lattice Theory of Quantum Gravity, **2026**, arXiv:2604.05641 [hep-th].
- [7.] --- Rovelli,C.,: Loop Quantum Gravity. In: Living Reviews in Relativity. 11 (**2008**), Nr. 5, doi:10.12942/lrr-2008-5.
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12. Non-scientific comment:

“Cosmology belongs to the greatest adventures of thought and research. Its history of development marks a gigantic elaboration of horizon.“

Rüdiger Vaas.

13. Verification:

This paper definitely is written without support from an AI, LLM or chatbot like Grok or Chat GPT 4 or other artificial tools. It is fully, purely human work in every universe.

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